

SCHOOL OF PHILOSOPHY
BACHELOR'S DEGREE IN EAST ASIAN STUDIES

**A cultural and sinographic study of *nǚshū*: The
only writing system created by and for women
in China.**

女书文化及女书字体研究：一种特由中国女性创
造并使用的文字。

Bachelor's Dissertation
Academic year 2020-2021

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June 2021

Abstract

This research aims to analyse the cultural and linguistic aspects related to *nǚshū*, the women's script which emerged in Jiangyong region (Hunan, China). Issues related to the lives of Yao women will be addressed, especially their childhood, sisterhood relationships and marriage system, as well as aspects concerning the dialect and this form of writing. Through the study of the characters' formation, in addition to the texts' formats, structure and recurring topics, it is intended to make an approach which allows us to understand this community's way of life and the reasons why this form of writing emerged. For this purpose, various research, mostly from Chinese sources, have been consulted, which offer precise information about the social and linguistic situation of this area, as well as testimonies and texts produced by women. This allows us to know the importance of the *nǚshū* as a creator of female collective consciousness and as a tool which allowed them to express their feelings within a context of patriarchal oppression.

Keywords: Nǚshū, Jiangyong, Xiangnan Tuhua, Women's script, ritual sisterhood, China.

Thanks to Hu Senyan for his help and unconditional support; without you, this
work would not have been possible.

感谢胡森彦，有了你的协助及无条件的支持，我才能完成论文。

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1. Introduction

In recent years, my academic interests have focused on the study of the Chinese language, and as a consequence my curiosity about various aspects of Chinese culture has steadily increased. During my first encounters with Chinese, I came across *nǚshū* purely by chance, and from that moment I felt the need to investigate it. However, until now I had neither the time, the resources, nor the necessary knowledge to approach the subject. After spending some time reading various documents, my initial idea of studying the cultural context that made the development of this writing system possible gradually evolved into a deeper interest in the writing system itself, its characters, and texts. This shift was mainly due to the fact that the cultural features surrounding *nǚshū* have already been discussed by Western researchers, yet their works contain very little information about its written characteristics. This led me to ask new questions and to investigate the subject in greater depth. In doing so, I discovered that in China numerous books and theses have been published that address precisely those aspects that interested me. For this reason, I decided to modify the original purpose of my research.

Nǚshū 女书, a term composed of the characters for “woman” and “writing,” is the only known writing system used exclusively by women in China. Although its origins are uncertain and we lack information about who created this system and their motivations, it was the women of the Jiangyong area (Hunan, China) who contributed to its development and spread until the arrival of the Communist Revolution, when it entered a phase of decline and gradual disappearance. Despite current efforts by the local population to promote its knowledge both within and outside the country, *nǚshū* can be considered an endangered writing system. The last native women who used it out of necessity have already passed away, but there are still women who learn it to keep the script alive and to teach it to anyone interested.

Although this writing system is generally little known both within China and internationally, the topic holds significant relevance, primarily of a social rather than practical nature. Studying *nǚshū* allows us to gain a better understanding of the lifestyle and thought processes of women belonging to a specific community within China. Furthermore, it helps us comprehend possible processes of character formation and the importance of language (dialect) in the daily lives of these people. Thus, the responsibility falls on us, sinologists, to approach and investigate the subject from multiple angles and

perspectives, so that it can reach and spark the interest of a wider audience. To this end, studies have examined *nǚshū* in relation to highly specific and diverse aspects, such as textile design, religion, and the tradition of foot-binding. Giving visibility to this women's script is an effective way to assist the local population in preventing its disappearance.

Despite the scarcity of specialised research on *nǚshū* conducted in the West, its cultural background has been the aspect most frequently addressed in books and academic theses. Among these works is «*Nǚshū (Chinese Women's Script) Literacy and Literature*» by Cathy Silber (1995), which focuses primarily on gender issues, that is, social aspects related to women, such as their lives, practices, and literature. Another notable work is the thesis by William Wei Chiang (1991), «*“We two know the script; we have become good friends” : Linguistic and Social Aspects of Women's Script Literacy in Southern Hunan, China*», which stands out for the wide variety of features it examines and for being one of the first field studies conducted by Western researchers after the public rediscovery of this script. My initial interest in the written and phonetic aspects of *nǚshū* arose from reading this latter work, although many of my arguments are based on another study devoted almost entirely to these topics. This work, published in 1986 by Gong Zhebing under the title «*Women's Script and Qianjiadong of the Yao Ethnic Group*» 《*妇女文字和瑶族千家峒*》, collects testimonies from various Chinese researchers who studied the social, linguistic, and written situation in different counties within my area of study.

Although these three works are fundamental for understanding the context surrounding the women's writing system, there are many other theses and articles—more or less specialised on the topic—that can help us refine certain features. Others can provide somewhat more up-to-date data, allowing us to compare information gathered from previous readings. Among these, particular attention should be given to Fei-Wen Liu, Wang Ping, and some Chinese Master's students, as all of them have made highly valuable contributions to the global study of *nǚshū*.

1.1. Objectives and methodology

My research has two main objectives. The first is to provide a basic overview of the geographical and cultural context of *nǚshū*. This section addresses five issues: the delineation of the study area, the origin of this writing system, the reasons behind its decline during the past century, and its role within female relationships, and the local marital system. The latter two points aim to demonstrate its importance at different stages in the lives of women of the Yao ethnic group. By saying “basic overview,” I intend to convey that there are far more extensive studies on each of the aspects discussed here. Therefore, in the first part of my research, only concise information on these matters will be presented, without going into excessive detail.

The second objective is to investigate in greater depth the phonetic (dialect) and written (characters) aspects of the script. This section examines the characteristics of the local dialect represented by the characters, the process of forming the graphemes (called *nǚzì* 女字), and other aspects related to text production, such as the uses of the script depending on the medium, its structure and poetic devices, and recurring themes in the texts. All of these aspects will be addressed in the third part of this work, providing more extensive and detailed explanations.

Regarding the methodology, once *nǚshū* was chosen as the main topic of my work and taking into account the ongoing pandemic, the only viable method was to conduct a bibliographic review. In a more favourable context, field research might have been possible, but currently the most appropriate approach is to compare the available databases and written testimonies. Therefore, this research is based on the analysis and comparison of books, original written and typographic sources, authors’ theories, and features that are not only sociocultural but also linguistic, drawn from different communities living in inland China.

In summary, this work aims not only to present some of the cultural aspects known to both Western and Eastern sinologists, but also to adopt a more intimate and local perspective, focusing on those aspects that are directly related to the creation of this unique writing system in the world.

2. Geographical and cultural context

Nǚshū 女书 script emerged in China and spread across a very specific area of the country; it was used exclusively by women living in several villages within Hunan Province. Yongzhou 永州 is one of the thirteen prefectures of this province, and within it lies Jiangyong County 江永县, formerly known as Yongming 永明, the same name as one of the rivers that flows through it. There, the town of Shangjiangxu 上江圩, can be considered the main centre of this practice, although it also spread to nearby localities. These include the villages of Xiaoli 峒里村 and Tianguangdong 田广洞村 to the east, Xiawan 夏湾村, Jinjiang 锦江村, Jianghe 江河村 and Baishui 白水村 to the south; and Puwei 浦尾村, Jingtian 荆田村 and Tongkou 桐口村 to the north (figure 1)¹. All of these villages are situated on or near the banks of the Xiaojiang River 消江河 to the south and Yongming River 永明河 to the north, in a rural area dominated by mountainous landscapes, resulting in very cold winters. While the topography hindered mobility to other regions, the distance between these villages was relatively short, making it possible to travel by foot, on animals, or in palanquins..

Shangjiangxu was the centre of county power, where governmental institutions representing all the small towns of the county were located². Chiang's 1991 research indicates that at that time the entire region comprised 46 towns, 4,804 families, and a total population of 18,958 inhabitants. Earlier studies cited in the first chapter of Gong's 1986 work provide more specific data for some of the aforementioned localities. These figures show that municipalities farther south from Shangjiangxu had several hundred more inhabitants than the neighbouring villages, which averaged approximately 430 residents³.

¹ Chiang, W. W. (1991), pp. 26-27. Gong, Z. (1986).

² Chiang, Op. cit., pp. 47.

³ See sections 7-12 (pp. 124-142) of *jǔshì hǎnjiàn de fùnǚ wénzì* 举世罕见的妇女文字 (A Rare Women's Script in the World). In: Gong, Z. (1986).

Figure 1: Location of the study area for this research.

The ethnic composition of this area is a mixture of Han 汉族 and Yao 瑶族 communities. The Yao are one of the 56 ethnic groups officially recognised by the Chinese government, with communities spread across the provinces of Guangxi, Hunan, Yunnan, Guangdong, Guizhou, and Jiangxi. The name of this community was officially adopted after the establishment of the People's Republic of China, although they refer to themselves by other terms. The earliest records mentioning them date back approximately 2,000 years, when they were categorised as the “southern barbarians” (*nánmán* 南蛮)⁴. According to these records, some Yao groups maintain the belief that they originate from Qianjiadong 千家峒, a mythical place located in the mountains of Jiangyong, where their ancestors lived⁵. Tradition holds that the Yao were guided southward by the Han from the central Yangtze River region⁶. Later, during the 7th century, there was a massive

⁴ Litzinger, R. A. (1995), pp. 124.

⁵ Ver Gong, Z. (1986).

⁶ Wiens, H. J. (1967), pp. 51-52, 96-100, como se citó en Chiang, Op. cit., pp. 35.

influx of Han settlers into the area inhabited by the Yao, which caused part of the local population to flee but also gradually led to the Sinicization of this group⁷. In this way, the two ethnicities began to intertwine both their customs and genealogical records, shaping the unique identity of this community.

Some of the features that allow us to identify this group as Yao include their veneration of the figure Pan Hu 盤瓠, certain festivals, ritualised sisterhood relationships, Taoist beliefs, and the *búluòfūjiā* 不落夫家⁸. In addition, women in this community are highly skilled in traditionally female activities such as embroidery (*nǚgōng* 女工) and tend to favour the colours black, red, blue, cyan, and white. Each colour can convey different attitudes toward life; for example, blue is considered a symbol of tranquillity⁹. They also use singing as a means of emotional expression as well as a way to record historical and personal events. One of the factors that has ensured the continuity of their culture and customs is the composition of songs, many of which have been passed down to subsequent generations through *nǚshū*¹⁰.

Nǚshū was a writing system created exclusively by and for the women of this area, and it was they who ensured its survival across generations. The cultural context of this region was particularly conducive to the flourishing of the women's script, as sisterhood relationships and the marital system in place before the Communist Revolution facilitated communication among women. Young women who knew *nǚshū* taught it to their sisters or to the women living in their husband's household. These women, in turn, passed on their knowledge to others, contributing to the development and spread of the script. Despite the ongoing threats of disappearance that *nǚshū* faced throughout the past century, a small number of writings and artifacts produced by women have survived to the present day. Thanks to these, we have been able to gain insight into the way of life practiced by this community and the concerns of its female inhabitants.

⁷ Liu F. W. (2004b), pp. 251.

⁸ Ibid., pp. 250-251.

⁹ Chen, H. (2013), pp. 46.

¹⁰ Ibid., pp. 24.

2.1. Theories about its origin

The origin of *nǚshū* remains a mystery for researchers to this day. There are many different theories, but there are no historical records that allow us to determine with certainty the period in which it emerged or whether a single person or multiple individuals created the characters. Some researchers base their arguments on the form of the characters, suggesting that *nǚshū* is a derivation of Chinese characters—a topic that will be discussed in more detail later. I personally agree with this theory, as the similarities are so striking that they cannot be mere coincidence. Nevertheless, this does not provide an exact date for its invention. Building on this theory, my research will analyse the points that *nǚshū* shares with and those that distinguish it from standard Chinese writing. While I consider this perspective the most suitable for establishing a possible origin, it is still interesting to consider other hypotheses based on local legends.

The most widespread of these local theories claims that the script was created during the reign of Emperor Huizong 徽宗 of the Song Dynasty 宋朝 (960–1279) by a young woman named Hu Yuxiu 胡玉秀. This girl from Jiangyong was renowned for her literary talent, which earned her the favour of the Emperor, who requested that she go to the Court to become his concubine. However, her life in the palace was very harsh. The women residing there mocked her literary abilities, which seemed to surpass her feminine virtues. For this reason, she felt the need to communicate with her family to express the situation she was experiencing. Being the Emperor's concubine, her life was constantly monitored, so she invented the *nǚshū* characters as a secret writing system that the guards did not discover¹¹. This theory, however, is quite confusing. Wei (1986: 131-132), who conducted field research in Xiawan, provides alternative local anecdotes. There it is said that the eldest brother of a girl surnamed Hu 胡 created the script for her because he could not bear to see her so sad and lonely. If a man had invented it, it would better explain the similarity of *nǚshū* characters to Chinese characters. However, this story is set during the Tang Dynasty 唐朝 (618-906). Wei also recounts a similar story about an unknown girl who lived during the Song Dynasty, though no additional details are provided about her.

Other, less widespread theories suggest that the origin of the characters lies in embroidery on fabric, or even that an ancient and unknown ethnic group invented the

¹¹ Liu, F. W. (2004a), pp. 425, (2010), pp. 246.

script as a form of communication before adopting Chinese characters¹². Since some of the characters show certain similarities to those inscribed on oracle bones and bronze artifacts (see section 3.2), other researchers speculate that *nǚshū* could date back to the Shang Dynasty 商朝 (approximately 1600-1050 BCE). However, after analysing the script, I believe that very few characters resemble those from that period, making this theory rather tenuous. A final hypothesis, which I consider much more plausible, is that the script was invented during the Ming Dynasty 明朝 (1368-1644)¹³. This claim is supported by the fact that the few surviving documents date from a relatively recent period. If *nǚshū* had a history spanning centuries or even millennia, one would expect a larger number of documents from different eras to have survived in varying conditions, which is not the case. Unfortunately, it is impossible to determine its exact origin from the evidence currently available, and thus it remains an unresolved mystery.

2.2. Childhood and sworn sisterhood relationships

In traditional China, the status of women was lower than that of men in both the public and private spheres. From childhood, girls were expected to learn their place in society and within the family. Their behaviour was closely tied to the Confucian values of the “Three Obediences and Four Virtues” (*sāncóngsidé* 三从四德). The three obediences were based on filial piety and the subordination of the female figure to the male: first to the father during childhood (*wèijiàcóngfū* 未嫁从父), then to the husband after marriage (*jìjiàcóngfū* 既嫁从夫), and finally to the son in widowhood (*fūsǐcóngzǐ* 夫死从子). The four virtues concerned maintaining ethical behaviour (*fùdé* 妇德), speaking modestly (*fùyán* 妇言), presenting oneself appropriately (*fùróng* 妇容), and performing household duties perfectly (*fùgōng* 妇功).

Girls from families with at least moderate socioeconomic status were expected to follow the tradition of foot-binding. Originally a Han practice, it was also observed in areas inhabited by ethnic minorities, such as Jiangyong. The practice involved deforming the foot to achieve a shape resembling a lotus flower bud, approximately 10 centimetres long (*sāncùnjīnlián* 三寸金莲). The goal was to increase the woman’s value for marriage

¹² Chiang, Op. cit., pp. 109-111.

¹³ Lee, A. G. (2008), pp. 159.

and secure a union beneficial to her family. Mothers supervised the process to ensure that the foot became as small and perfect as possible. In contrast, girls from very poor families allowed their feet to grow naturally. Without bound feet, they had little marital value and were often sold as secondary wives or domestic servants—the lowest status within the household. Some girls bound their feet temporarily until marriage, as they needed mobility to assist their husbands with farm work.

Foot-binding marked the transition from childhood to adulthood. While in other regions of China the process typically began between the ages of four and nine—before the foot had fully developed—in Jiangyong it was performed when girls were three or four years old¹⁴. The procedure was so painful that it was often started during the cold season, so that the low temperatures would numb the feet and alleviate the pain. As Lisa See recounts in her book *«Snow Flower and the Secret Fan»* (2006: 35), one in ten girls died from foot-binding each year across China, highlighting the dangers of this practice.

The division of labour was established from this point onward, as girls could not leave the house due to their limited mobility, while boys were expected to begin working in the fields. According to Wang (2000: 162), *nǚshū* texts make no reference to foot-binding because it was considered “*as natural and indispensable as the limbs, eyes, nose, and other parts of the body*”, so that women internalised it as “*a code to seek and recognise their female companions*”. The ideal of the lotus foot was not merely a sexual attribute that gave women value, but also a symbol that allowed them to create and participate in a shared group consciousness.

The formation of ritualised sisterhoods was originally a Han tradition and thus occurred in different parts of China with their own characteristics. These bonds were so important in Chinese social relations that they existed not only among girls (*jiébàizǐmèi* 结拜姊妹), but also among boys (*jiébàixiōngdì* 结拜兄弟). While these bonds were typically formed between people of the same sex, Chiang (1991: 62) notes that it was possible for them to occur between individuals of different sexes, although I personally have not found any evidence supporting this.

In Jiangyong, there were two types of bonds among girls. The first was the ritualised sisterhood, or *jiébàizǐmèi* 结拜姊妹, which was usually formed between at least two

¹⁴ Wang, P. (2000), pp. 164. Wei, Y. (1986), pp. 130.

adolescent girls or women, typically of the same generation. The only requirement was that each participant contribute 50 *jīn* 斤 (25 kilograms) of rice. The collected amount was sold in portions whenever a member of the sisterhood married, and the money was used to purchase gifts for the bride. The sisterhood usually dissolved when the last girl in the group married¹⁵, as living in their husbands' households left them with few opportunities to meet.

To form this bond, girls could voluntarily propose individuals they felt close to as their sisters. They also gathered on special occasions, such as the Lantern Festival (*yuánxiāojié* 元宵节) or the festival celebrating the Ox's birthday (*dòuniújié* 斗牛节), to spend time together and get to know one another. Activities included cooking and singing, as well as showcasing their skills in embroidery and *nǚshū*¹⁶, so that friendships formed during these gatherings could lead to the establishment of new sisterhoods.

The ideal sisterhood consisted of seven sisters (*qīzīmèi* 七姊妹 possibly because the number seven is considered auspicious in Chinese tradition for relationships, as its pronunciation (*qī* 七) resembles that of "equal" (*qí* 齐), and the purpose of the bond was to unite equals. Forming a seven-member sisterhood increased a woman's value in arranging her marriage, whereas failure to do so was seen as a humiliation for her family and her husband's family. Girls from very poor families were allowed to forgo the rice contribution. Any woman interested, regardless of surname, generation, age, or marital status, could join the group¹⁷, so reaching the number seven seemed relatively easy. However, according to the information collected by Dorer (1993: 87-90, 93)¹⁸ and the surviving texts, it was most common that this ideal was not fully achieved.

None of the surviving testimonies make reference to seven-member groups, so Silber (1995: 91-92) hypothesises that this could be interpreted as a form of resistance to marriage. Personally, I find this unlikely. It is true that in other regions of China, such as Guangdong, girls openly defied the marital system through collective suicides or by taking heterosexual chastity vows¹⁹. In contrast, the testimonies of women from Jiangyong do not show signs of defiance against imposed values, but rather simple

¹⁵ Silber, C. (1995), pp. 89-90.

¹⁶ Zhao, L. (1986), pp. 81-82.

¹⁷ Xie, Z. (1991), pp. 1875-1876, as cited in Silber, Op. cit., pp. 91.

¹⁸ As cited in Silber, Op. cit., pp. 89.

¹⁹ See Sankar, A. (1978).

complaints directed at their sisters in search of comfort. Furthermore, Chiang (1991: 207) reports that young men often helped their brothers improve their relationships with the person assigned to them by the matchmaker, demonstrating obedience and camaraderie rather than resistance to marriage.

The second type of relationship—peer relationships, called *lǎotóng* 老同 (“older equal”) or *tóngnián* 同年 (“same year”)—was not exclusive to the Yao; other ethnic groups such as the Zhuang 壮族 and the Buyi 布依族 had similar practices²⁰. These relationships were established between two girls born in the same year and, if possible, in the same month and day. Ideally, the girls would live in different municipalities and come from families with similar socioeconomic backgrounds, having the same number of siblings born in the same order and with the same sexes. For the relationship to be considered perfect, the girls were expected to have the same height and foot size, as well as similar beauty and personality²¹, making these bonds much more intimate.

According to information collected by Silber and Dorer from informants such as Yi Nianhua 义年华 (1906-1991), one of the last women who knew *nǚshū* after its rediscovery, girls could have more than one *lǎotóng* at the same time²². This does not mean that any girl could become her soulmate; they were usually very selective in this regard. For example, a *nǚshū* expert named Gao Shupi 高树批, stated: “*I was very selective. I agreed [to form the bond] only in cases of very pretty and proper girls. I didn’t accept others... Afterwards, we wore the same clothing, and the same earrings and shoes*”²³; Yi Nianhua also commented on this aspect: “*The good ones matched with the good ones, the ugly with the ugly, the smart ones with the smart ones, just like husband and wife*”²⁴. These relationships could be arranged by the parents with other families before the babies were born, or through the intervention of a matchmaker, as was also the case with marriages.

When the girls reached preadolescence (around 10 years old), a suitable girl was suggested to become her *lǎotóng*. If she agreed, she sent a proposal written in *nǚshū* on a fan. To accept, the other girl had to send another letter in the same format. The fan, along

²⁰ Shang, B. (1985), pp. 17-18, as cited in Silber, Op. cit., pp. 64.

²¹ Wang, Op. cit., pp. 166. Silber, C. (1994), pp. 51.

²² Silber (1995), Op. cit., pp. 65.

²³ Dorer (1993), pp. 83, as cited in Silber (1995), Op. cit., pp. 65.

²⁴ Silber (1995), Op. cit., pp. 65.

with other gifts such as shoes or sweets, was part of the exchange that took place after the bond was established. Below is an excerpt from a letter written by He Xijing 何西静, in which she accepts the proposal of another girl to become sisters:

接下慢讲读几道 听得心欢心自红
I have read your letter slowly several times, and my heart glows with joy.

句句轻言本有理 合意娣娘邀结交
Each line is gentle and reasonable; you invite me to form a bond as sisters.

天仙配成咱二人 难得尔身是不嫌
Our pairing was ordained by Heaven; I am honoured that you chose me.

尔到低门住几日 我又粗心侍过了
You have come to visit for several days, yet I have served you clumsily.

自从分开如水乱 难舍难离别尔身
Since we parted, my heart has been turbulent like flowing water; it is hard to bear
our separation.

我就千行难比尔 望日量宽请不嫌
I am not as capable as you in a thousand ways; please be patient with me.

大齐可怜烦心大 二个陪齐人解人
We both carry sorrows and hardships; when we are together, we comfort each
other.

小取名声为结拜 本是千行不认真
We are known as ritual sisters, yet this bond is taken lightly in the ways of the
world.

耐久陪齐算解意 尽有忧愁人惜人
From time to time, we console each other, sharing our troubles and caring for one
another.

.....

我把二人结为义 本是前生的有缘
Becoming ritual sisters between us was predestined in our previous lives.²⁵

Here we can observe a distinctive feature in how the women addressed themselves and their counterparts. They often praised the virtues of the other while referring to themselves in a self-deprecating manner, as a sign of courtesy and modesty. In these letters, the girls typically compared their family circumstances, the quality of their writing, or their observance of rituals²⁶, using formulas that placed the writer in an inferior position. Although the communication seems to occur between two individuals in different hierarchical positions, it in fact unites two equal souls—two women who understand

²⁵ Translated by the author. Chiang, *Op. cit.*, pp. 403-407.

²⁶ Silber (1994), *Op. cit.*, pp. 55.

moral values and know how to behave both within the community and toward the person most precious to them.

Once the bond was formalised, appointments and visits were arranged during local or national festivals, such as the Dragon Boat Festival (*duānwūjié* 端午节). After several meetings, they were allowed to spend a few days together to continue strengthening their ties. On these occasions, the two girls would sleep together and dress in the same clothing²⁷, symbolising the deep union of two kindred spirits who could share everything.

Communication between the girls was a key component of their relationship. They tried to maintain contact throughout their lives, and the affection they felt for one another was expressed primarily through messages sent during times of need. Even when they could not see each other as often as they wished, they sought to comfort and assist their sister when necessary. In the letters, feelings were expressed more openly than in spoken language, which is typically subtle and ambiguous. The girls often employed implicit and explicit analogies commonly symbolising marriage. One such image is that of a pair of mandarin ducks (*yīduìyuānyāng* 一对鸳鸯), a symbol of fidelity. Their intent was to show that their relationship was as enduring and intimate as that of a loving couple²⁸.

The following two excerpts illustrate the communication between Hu Cizhu 胡慈珠 and Tang Baozhen 唐宝珍. Tang received a consoling letter from her older sister in response to an unfortunate event in her life and immediately sent a reply:

静坐房前透夜想 耐久起心薄奉言

I sit quietly in my room, lost in thoughts through the night; after a while, I gather my courage and decide to write to you.

把笔写书双流泪 急跨回家劝姑娘

I take up my brush, and tears flow as I write. I hasten home to send you words of comfort.

.....

尔夫二月落阴府 八月中秋来劝言

Your husband passed away in February; I send you consolation in August.

就是姑娘不怪我 我也自知礼来迟

Even if you do not blame me, I know my words have arrived late.

²⁷ Silber (1995), Op. cit., pp. 67.

²⁸ Silber (1995), Op. cit., pp. 75-76.

一吧修书来劝解 二接妹娘过中秋

First, I wish to comfort you with my letter; second, I hope to invite you to spend the Mid-Autumn Festival with me.

到我家中住几日 小说小言解开心

Stay with me for a few days; we will talk, share stories, and ease our hearts.

.....

姊解尔愁如刻诉 身体不强取回家

I wish to relieve your sorrow as if carving it out; if your health is weak, I will take you home.

好不同村同屋住 时刻坐齐人导人

We could live together, comforting each other at all times.

[Reply]

来在贵家出得气 始邀结交姊妹行

I can vent my sorrow in your home; this is why we are ritual sisters.

几人结交同来往 咱算亲生姊妹行

We, ritual sisters, are as close as natural sisters.

上又没得乘凉树 下又没得靠背山

Above us, there are no trees to shade us; below, no mountains to support us.

.....

自坐空房如孤鸟 女是出乡无用人

I sit alone in my empty room, like a solitary bird; women who leave their home have no use.²⁹

The girls spent most of their time in the rooms on the upper floor of the house, an area reserved exclusively for them, which is why they were called “women of the upper floor” (*lóushàngnǚ* 楼上女)³⁰. There, they typically engaged in embroidery, singing, and whispered about women’s matters. If any of the girls—or their relatives—knew *nǚshū*, they could teach the others to read and write. In general, learning this form of writing took place during the winter. The method they used was as follows: the girl who knew the script would recite a verse while her sisters traced the characters in the text, and then all together they would repeat it and try to identify the characters. This process was repeated for each verse until the text was fully understood³¹, after which they could practice and refine their calligraphy to send letters to their sisters and relatives.

²⁹ Translated by the author. Chiang, *Op. cit.*, pp. 375-381, 392-393.

³⁰ Chiang, *Op. cit.*, pp. 40.

³¹ Chiang, *Op. cit.*, pp. 146. Huang, H. (1986), pp. 140.

2.3. Marriage

Before the Communist Revolution and the subsequent reform of the marital system in China, the Yao ethnic group living in the Jiangyong area followed a particular marriage process divided into five stages. Their traditional system was called *bùluòfūjiā* 不落夫家, literally translated as “not falling into the husband’s house,” referring to a delayed patrilocal system. The bride did not move permanently to her husband’s home after the wedding; instead, she resided there for three days and then returned to her own home, where she stayed until the end of her pregnancy. The maximum time she could remain in her natal home after the wedding was three years; otherwise, her husband’s parents would arrange another marriage for their son. During this period, several visits to the husband’s home were planned to coincide with important festivals, such as the New Year³², to help the bride become pregnant and gradually adapt to her new household.

In general, the Chinese marital system was summarised by the expression *fùmǔ zhī mìng, méishuò zhī yán* 父母之命，媒妁之言³³, literally “orders of the parents and words of the matchmakers.” This indicates that there were mainly two ways to arrange marriages. The first was the decision made by two families before the birth of the babies. The sex of the babies determined whether they would become sworn siblings (same sex) or a future couple (different sex)³⁴. The other method was through the intervention of a matchmaker, who recommended boys to the respective families and oversaw the entire process. While a fundamental factor determining the union was the shape of the girl’s feet, it was also important that the two young people were fully compatible. This was checked by comparing their eight characters, corresponding to their exact birth dates. In this way, the personality, virtues, faults, and mutual affinity of each individual were inferred.

The five stages of the marriage process were as follows:

Hiring a relative (*jiéqīn* 结亲) or Promise to give the daughter (*xǔnǚ* 许女). This involved finding a suitable person to act as an intermediary and carry out the formalities of the union, even if the couple had already met. If they had never met, a meeting was arranged on an auspicious date. If the young man was pleased with the assigned bride, he

³² Silber, C. (1994), pp. 398.

³³ Huang, Xuefei (1986), pp. 124.

³⁴ Wei, Op. cit., pp. 130.

would give her a sum of money as a gift, and if she accepted it, it signified her approval as well. After this meeting, the young man's family would choose a propitious date for the engagement within a year. On that day, gifts were exchanged between the families, and the groom carried a piece of red paper on which the bride's eight characters were written³⁵.

Delivery of the date (*sòng rì zǐ* 送日子). When the groom's family decided on a wedding date, they had to deliver this information in writing on a piece of red paper along with other gifts to the bride's family. If the bride's parents agreed with the chosen date, the groom's family would announce it in their village so that no one else would hold any celebrations on that day³⁶.

Hair collection (*shàng tóu* 上头). The hairstyle a girl wore at each stage of her life symbolised her marital status. One month before the wedding, she had to change her hairstyle again to indicate that she was about to be married. At this stage, the groom's family sent a quantity of glutinous rice, which was distributed among the bride's relatives and other families in the village as a way to invite them to the celebration. Unmarried girls and the bride's ritual sisters gathered at her home to sing from one month to three days before the ceremony. This tradition was called *zuò gē táng* 坐歌堂, meaning "sitting in the hall and singing"³⁷, or *kū gē* 哭歌, meaning "crying and singing"³⁸.

Obtaining the bride (*tǎo qīn* 讨亲). On the wedding day, the bride dressed in a wedding outfit made by herself and wore a silver headdress, usually adorned with figures of the phoenix and the dragon³⁹. Before she could sit in the so-called flower chair (*huā qiáo* 花桥), which was carried by the wedding procession to her husband's home, she had to participate in another tradition called *chàng shuǎ gē* 唱耍歌, which involved crying while singing to her relatives to thank them for their kindness and affection. She also had to pay respects to her ancestors. Afterwards, she was transported to her husband's village, where the marriage was formalised in the temple and followed by a banquet. From the wedding night onward, the couple was expected to sleep together in the same room⁴⁰.

³⁵ Chiang, Op. cit., pp. 56-58.

³⁶ Chiang, Op. cit., pp. 58.

³⁷ Ibid., pp. 58-60.

³⁸ Liu (2004a), Op. cit., pp. 433. Zhao, Op. cit., pp. 82.

³⁹ Wei, Op. cit., pp. 131.

⁴⁰ Chiang, Op. cit., pp. 60. Huang, Xuefei, Op. cit., pp. 124-125.

On the third day of the celebration, her sisters and relatives presented her with a book called *sānzhāoshū* 三朝书 (Book of the Third Day), which contained pre-written messages of good fortune and a description of the bride's virtues and faults, serving as an introduction to her husband's family.

Reception of the third morning (*jiēsānzhāo* 接三朝). This stage began on the third day after the ceremony, when the bride could return to her natal village. From that moment, she stayed with her family and made occasional visits to her husband until the birth of the child, when she had to move permanently to her in-laws' home. Due to the frequent visits and travel, the local dialect used the term "female visitor" (*nǚkè* 女客) to refer to newly married women⁴¹. After settling in her husband's house, the bride only returned to her natal home during certain annual festivals, including the Bird-Expelling Festival (*gǎnniǎojié* 赶鸟节), the New Harvest Festival (*chángxīnjié* 尝新节), and the Ghost Festival (*guǐjié* 鬼节)⁴².

Women longed to have male children because this would raise their status within their husband's family. This was especially beneficial during their years of widowhood, when their son had already reached adulthood and contributed to the family economy. In such cases, their status could even rise to that of head of the household if their son held them in great respect. Life expectancy at that time was not as high as it is today, and the population was frequently exposed to periods of famine and numerous diseases. Therefore, if some misfortune occurred and the husband died before she gave birth to a son, or if she already had one but he was still too young to work, the woman could remarry another man who would support the family. However, the situation seems to have varied depending on the traditions of each municipality. According to Wei (1986: 131), in Xiawan women were not allowed to remarry, and if they dared to do so, their husband's family could bring them back and force them to remain with them, a practice known as *qiǎngqī* 抢妻 ("wife seizure"). By contrast, Zhang (1986: 134) mentions that in Puwei it was permitted as long as the woman received the consent of her husband's family and paid them a certain amount of money to compensate for the bride price they had paid for her. If everyone agreed, the woman could remarry her husband's brother and remain within the same family.

⁴¹ Chiang, Op. cit., pp. 60-61.

⁴² Chiang, Op. cit., pp. 52-53. Huang, Xuefei, Op. cit., pp. 126-127.

At that time, people commonly believed in the theory that the soul is immortal (*línghúnbúmiè* 灵魂不灭). This belief held that after the death of the body, the soul continued to live in the afterlife for eternity. For this reason, women often requested that their texts written in *nǚshū* be burned after their death so that the words could accompany them into the other world. In some cases, although less common, they might also ask for some of their texts to be burned after the death of their husband so that a part of them would always remain with him⁴³. This is one of the main reasons why so few *nǚshū* pieces have survived to the present day.

2.4. Decline and rediscovery

As the twentieth century progressed, Chinese women gradually gained more rights and opportunities to advance and place themselves on a more equal status with men. Practices such as foot-binding were abolished thanks to the efforts of associations that defended women's rights⁴⁴. Women progressively gained access to education: initially to basic instruction and forms of education specifically designed for women, and later to higher education based on the learning of Chinese characters and other subjects that had previously been considered “men's affairs”⁴⁵. However, this promising panorama of social change, combined with political conflicts, led to the gradual decline of *nǚshū*.

The establishment of the communes in 1958 brought women into economic activities, which meant that the time they could devote to traditional female practices became very limited. Later, beginning in 1966, the Cultural Revolution led by Mao Zedong took place. This ten-year campaign aimed to destroy the country's old traditions, which were considered contrary to the dominant ideology of the time. For this reason, *nǚshū*, along with other religious practices, was banned.⁴⁶ Women who knew the script—referred to during this period as “demonic characters” (*yāozì* 妖字)—had to abandon it temporarily and hide their texts so that they would not be destroyed. If they were discovered, they risked being judged as “demons” (*yāonǚ* 妖女)⁴⁷.

⁴³ Huang, H., Op. cit., pp. 141.

⁴⁴ Croll, E. (2011), pp. 51.

⁴⁵ Ibid., pp. 57.

⁴⁶ Chiang, Op. cit., pp. 101-102.

⁴⁷ In Chinese there are several ways to refer to demons or evil spirits, but this particular term was likely used because its pronunciation is similar to the name of this ethnic group. Xiao, S. (1986), pp. 142.

Nǚshū was rediscovered in the 1980s, but by then women no longer needed to use it because their role in society had completely changed. At that time, the media presented *nǚshū* as a “secret language”⁴⁸. However, it is not a language but rather a written, syllabic representation of the local dialect. Even today, some researchers and people interested in the topic believe that it was a secret script unknown to men. This idea can be challenged through the testimonies of authors such as Idema (2009: 4) or Liu (2004: 434⁴⁹), who note that several men are known to have learned to read or write *nǚshū* through their wives. Zhang (1986: 136) also states that both women and men could learn *nǚshū* if they wished, although most men simply were not interested. Perhaps women did try to conceal the content of their letters from their husbands, but the characters themselves were visible on the clothing they embroidered as well as in the Third-Day Books, which were publicly shown and read after weddings. The script was accepted by society and provided women with a means to express their feelings beyond the upper-floor rooms and convey them to the people most precious to them.

⁴⁸ Idema, W. (2009), pp. 3-4.

⁴⁹ Citing Tang, G. (1995).

3. Study of nǚshū as a writing system

3.1. Relationship with the dialect

The residents of Shangjiangxu and its surrounding areas have three Sinitic languages that they can use freely in their daily lives. The first is the country's official language, Mandarin, or *pǔtōnghuà* 普通话, which is mainly used in public and professional contexts due to its widespread use. Thanks to it, establishing relationships between regions whose local dialects differ becomes easier. However, not all inhabitants of the country are proficient in this language; younger people are more likely to use it, whereas many older individuals who grew up speaking their local dialect may not understand it. The second means of communication used is the traditional dialect of Hunan, called *xiāngyǔ* 湘语 or *húnánhuà* 湖南话, which is unintelligible to speakers of Mandarin or other dialects. It is one of the dialect groups officially recognised by the Chinese government and is used at the provincial level. The character *xiāng* 湘 functions as a synonym for “Hunan,” so there is no doubt when associating it with its area of use. The third language used in Jiangyong County is its own local dialect, called *xiāngnán tǔhuà* 湘南土话, a term that can be translated as “the native speech of southern Hunan.” It is mainly used in family and informal settings, and to a lesser extent in local public life. The characters of the women's script are a written representation of this dialect.

To study the phonetic aspects of this dialect, I consulted two theses (Chiang, 1991; Bai, 2019) and a book (Huang Xuezheng, 1993), and then compared the information with the content of the «*Dictionary of Standard Nǚshū Characters*», a digitised version of the work published by Gong y Tang (2003)⁵⁰. My conclusions are that *xiāngnán tǔhuà* has 21 consonants and 5 main vowels. The consonants are /p/, /p'/, /m/, /f/, /t/, /t'/, /n/, /l/, /k/, /k'/, /ŋ/, /tɕ/, /tɕ'/, /ŋ/, /ɕ/, /ts/, /ts'/, /s/, /h/, /y/, /v/. These appear in all the works consulted, with the exception of the following two cases:

- 1) There are discrepancies between /h/ y /x/ in some words. In the aforementioned dictionary, where standardised sounds are indicated, /h/ is used for sounds that were originally marked as /x/. For example, the original transcription for 喊 is /xa²¹/, whereas in the dictionary it appears as /ha²¹/. I

⁵⁰ See: The Nushu Coder's Group on GitHub (2018-2020): *zàixiàn nǚ shū zìdiǎn* 在线女书字典 (Online nǚshū dictionary). Retrieved April 8, 2021, from <https://nushuscript.org/>

have chosen to use /h/ because the sound /x/ may correspond to /ɕ/, and moreover this is not a phenomenon that occurs systematically.

- 2) Although I have decided to include the phonemes /y/ and /v/ (the latter corresponding to /w/) separately, some authors prefer to group both under the phoneme /ø/, while others do not consider these letters to be consonants but rather vowels.

On the other hand, the main vowels are /a/, /o/, /e/, /i/, /u/, although some authors also include /ə/ (similar to /a/), /ɔ/ (an open /o/), /ø/ (similar to /e/), /ɥ/ (/i/ in consonants like /z/ or /sh/), /u/ (similar to /u/), or consider the sounds /y/ and /v/ (/w/) to be vowels. I believe it is appropriate to select only the five main vowels, since the others can be considered variations in pronunciation of these. In this way, we can observe that there are differences between this dialect and Mandarin, as the latter consists of 23 consonants (including /y/ and /w/) and 6 vowels (including /ü/). However, they are not completely different from one another, as some correspondences can be established between their consonants, such as: /p/=b/, /t/=d/, /k/=g/, /tɕ/=j/, /tɕ'/=q/, /ɕ/=x/, /ts/=z/, /ts'/=c/.

Conducting an exact study of tones is quite difficult because each town presents variations in pronunciation, which has also led to differing opinions regarding tonality. Chiang and Huang Xuezhen indicate in their works that there were seven tones, but both the dictionary of characters and Bai's thesis—more recent sources—state that there are five. It is likely that the standardisation of *nǚshū* has also affected its phonetic features. In the dictionary, only the tones /21/, /33/, /35/, /42/ y /55/ appear, and it seems appropriate to use these five tones because others mentioned in earlier works are very similar to them. This tonal system expressed through numbers (*diào zhí* 调值) can also be represented using a system of symbols; both indicate the direction and duration of the voice during pronunciation. To understand these systems, we can observe figure 2. In the graph, each arrow represents the numbers (and corresponding symbols) used to indicate the standardised tones of this dialect. Their names in Chinese derive from the traditional system of eight tones, composed of the *yīn* 阴 and *yáng* 阳 categories of the tones *píng* 平 (level), *shàng* 上 (rising), *qù* 去 (falling), and *rù* 入 (entering).

Figure 2: The five tones of the *xiāngnán tǔhuà* dialect with their corresponding tonal symbols and tone number.

Thus, /21/ is a falling tone (去声) similar to the modern fourth tone, /33/ is a level tone (阴平) similar to the first tone, /35/ is a rising tone (上声) like the second tone, /42/ is also a falling tone but more pronounced than /21/ (in these studies it is considered a *yángpíng* 阳平), and /55/ is a level tone but very short in duration, pronounced with a brief glottal stop (*rùshēng* 入声).

According to Chiang (1991: 68-70), including all tonal variations, this dialect has 1,316 syllables commonly used in everyday life. However, it is not a fully standardised dialect; rather, there are numerous local subdialects that are mutually unintelligible among their speakers. In each of the municipalities within the area of study of this research, variations in pronunciation can be observed, with personal pronouns being a particularly notable example.

There is a significant discrepancy between the total number of syllables in *xiāngnán tǔhuà* and those represented in *nǚshū*, as this script records only 492 of the 1,316 syllables⁵¹. This difference is mainly due to the social limitations associated with this writing system, since its use was exclusively linked to the lives of women. As a result, the vocabulary is restricted to a limited number of expressions and recurring themes. Because it is a script that reflects a specific dialect, it did not spread throughout the country, and its area of use remained very small. Unlike Mandarin, it did not have the opportunity to adapt to the rapid social development that took place in twentieth-century

⁵¹ Chiang, Op. cit., pp. 112.

China, as it was banned after the establishment of the communist regime and only rediscovered later. During that time, it fell out of use, and some women secretly preserved documents and other objects on which these characters were written.

Although it was a script widespread among the women of the area, not all of them knew how to use it. Some were fortunate enough to learn to recite songs thanks to their female relatives or sworn sisters, but mastering both writing and reading required considerable practice and a strong capacity for interpretation. This is because a very limited number of characters were used to represent a much larger number of *hànzì* 汉字, meaning that it was the task of the writer or reader to assign a specific meaning to each character depending on the context. Although the choice of pronunciation and meaning for each character often relied on trial and error, fixed formulae could be very helpful when understanding a text, since their characters and readings remained constant.

Nǚshū was a form of writing used, on the one hand, to tell new stories and, on the other, to adapt and translate songs and folk tales from Mandarin Chinese into the local dialect. Women used it to write to their relatives and sworn sisters about their concerns in times of need, as well as to narrate their own experiences in autobiographical form. The most common written format was poetry, while orally it was expressed through singing due to the importance of the phonetic aspect of its characters. Since women at that time had very limited levels of education and literary culture, the precision and diversity of the vocabulary used in their texts cannot be compared with that of professional poets. Nevertheless, these women had the privilege of possessing the means to express their ideas and feelings in written form, something that was unthinkable for the vast majority of women in China.

In 1991, when Chiang conducted his field research and recorded his findings, the 492 syllables of *nǚshū* were represented by approximately 1,500 characters. Many of these were variations of the same basic character, representing the same *hànzì* and carrying the same meaning. For this reason, a later process of standardisation reduced the set to 396 basic characters according to Tsinghua University. Since in ancient times the number of characters available to express a wide range of ideas and feelings was quite limited, fixed formulae were employed to shorten sentence length while adapting to poetic patterns without losing part of the original meaning. In doing so, some characters were omitted or altered, and words from their own dialect were used to create these fixed

structures. For example, the formula 凭拢 is composed of the verb *píng* 凭 (/pai⁴²/ in *xiāngnán tǔhuà*), meaning “to depend on,” and the verb *lǒng* 拢 (/lon²¹/), which can mean “to gather.” This expression is a shortened way of conveying the idea of gathering (*jùjí zài yīqǐ* 聚集在一起) with fewer characters. Another example is 陪盛坐, composed of the verb *péi* 陪 (/p'eur⁴²/), meaning “to accompany,” the adjective *shèng* 盛 (/eion³³/) meaning “abundant,” and the verb *zuò* 坐 (/tseu²¹/) meaning “to sit”. This expression conveys the idea of a large group of people sitting together (*xǔduōrén péizhezuo* 许多人陪着坐), an activity frequently undertaken by sworn sisters to practice *nǚshū*, sing, or embroider⁵².

3.2. Formation of characters

Due to the existence of various theories regarding the origin of this writing system, the source of its characters can also be a controversial topic. However, authors such as Chiang and Gong suggest in their works that these characters may be an evolution or adaptation of *hànzì*, rather than the other way around as some researchers propose. To support this theory, they point to the similarities in form and pronunciation between certain *nǚshū* characters and their corresponding *hànzì*.

In this way, we can establish three main sources from which the forms of these characters may derive. The first of these is the shape of ancient *hànzì*. Among the forms adopted by characters during their evolution, particular attention should be given to those inscribed on oracle bones (*jiǎgǔwén* 甲骨文) and on bronze (*jīnwén* 金文). To demonstrate their relationship, we can compare the form of the following characters⁵³:

modern <i>hànzì</i>	ancient form	<i>Nǚshū</i> character
交		
步		
母		
水		

⁵² He, X. (2011), pp. 30.

⁵³ Adapted from Zhao, L. & Gong, Z. (1986), pp. 94.

Secondly, based on the shape of certain characters, we can infer a relationship between this script and elements of nature, although sometimes imagination is needed to establish this connection. Jiangyong is located in a rural area, so its municipalities are surrounded by flora and fauna, influencing this script. For example, we can see the shape of a bird in the character (食), which shows a mountain surrounded by trees.

Thirdly, as some scholars argue, we can observe the influence of *hànzì* on *nǚshū* characters in the following situations:

- 1) Characters identical in shape to their corresponding *hànzì* but written in a more curved style. Examples include (平).
- 2) Characters that are similar to *hànzì* but present certain differences. For instance, in (并) the vertical lines extend above the upper horizontal stroke rather than forming two independent strokes.
- 3) Characters whose components or strokes have been inverted or repositioned in comparison with their corresponding *hànzì*. The inversion may occur outward, as in (义).

⁵⁴ 公 corresponds to the ancient form, while 发 corresponds to the *nǚshū* character. Although they were originally two different characters, they display a very similar shape.

⁵⁵ Chen, H., *Op. cit.*, pp. 30, 48-49.

4) Characters that resemble *hànzì* but are written with fewer strokes. For example:

 4 strokes → 听 7 strokes
 4 strokes → 如 6 strokes

5) Characters whose structure is similar to that of their corresponding *hànzì* but which contain different components, such as (接).

The *nǚshū* script is composed of characters that represent a syllable and, in some cases, a specific meaning, so that several words pronounced in the same way in the dialect can be written with a single character. In other words, each character corresponds to a single pronunciation, unlike many Chinese characters. These ideograms have a distinctive diamond-like shape, where the upper right side forms the highest point and the lower left end the lowest. Because the strokes of these characters are more stylised and delicate than those of *hànzì*, they have been referred to as “tadpole script” (蝌蚪文), “mosquito-leg characters” (蚊脚字), “mosquito-and-ant characters” (蚊蚁字) or “long-leg script” (长脚文字)⁵⁶. The term *nǚzì* 女字 can be used more specifically to refer to the ideograms used in *nǚshū*, thus distinguishing them from the broader concept of Chinese characters.

Nǚzì are formed from nine types of basic strokes, five of which are very common while the others appear in a smaller number of characters. The main strokes are the left-slanting stroke .

In addition to the common alphabetical ordering, the total number of strokes used to write a given *nǚzì* can also serve as another way of classifying them. This criterion also allows us to observe how many characters are grouped within each category. The minimum number of strokes is one, while the maximum is twenty. When calculating the average distribution of characters according to their number of strokes, the largest group

⁵⁶ Liu (2004a), Op. cit., pp. 435.

⁵⁷ Wu, Y. (2013) 12-13, Ma, Op. cit., pp. 11.

corresponds to those composed of eight strokes. As the number of strokes increases or decreases beyond this point, the number of characters belonging to those groups also decreases⁵⁸.

Nǚzì can mainly be classified into two categories depending on whether they consist of a single component (*dútǐzì* 独体字) such as 𠂇 (天), or whether they are formed by two or more components (*hétǐzì* 合体字). In most characters belonging to the second group, the upper right part corresponds to the main component that forms the body of the character; it presents few variations and is larger than the lower left part, where the radical is placed and where more combinations occur⁵⁹. However, there are also characters composed of two or more different parts without a radical, such as 彳 (行) or 𠂇 (隐).

In Mandarin characters, the element that functions as a radical can provide semantic information. For example, 药 (medicine), 花 (flower), and 茶 (tea), share the radical 艹 derived from the character 草 (grass), which clearly indicates a relationship with vegetation. Unlike Mandarin, *nǚshū* radicals do not provide a specific meaning⁶⁰ nor do they allow characters to be classified into families of related words. This is mainly because, in most cases, a single *nǚzì* represents several Chinese characters that may be completely different from one another. For example, the character 𠂇 (/tso²¹/), with the radical 亻 represents the *hànzì* 在 (to be at, to exist), 再 (again), and 载 (year, record), whose radicals are 土, 冂, and 车 respectively. Although their pronunciations in Mandarin are quite similar, their meanings are completely different. In some cases, the radicals of *hànzì* and *nǚzì* coincide; however, this does not allow us to establish a direct correspondence between them, since a *nǚzì* usually represent several different *hànzì*. One example is the similarity between the radicals 纟 and 纟, as seen in 纟 (红) and 纟 (结, 织).

There is also a third type of character that could be included within the group of compound characters (*hétǐzì* 合体字), although they present certain differences. These characters do not contain a radical on the left side but instead consist of two identical components that may either face each other 𠂇 (悲) or be arranged so that they point in the same direction 𠂇 (亲). These could be referred to as double characters (*shuāngtǐzì* 双体

⁵⁸ Wu, Op. cit., pp 12.

⁵⁹ Ibid., pp. 12.

⁶⁰ Chen, J. (1986), pp. 53.

字)⁶¹. It is also possible to create characters following the principle of symmetry, either horizontally (星)⁶².

As for *nǚshū* radicals, they can be defined as simple forms located in the lower left part of the character. Some of them resemble radicals that can also be found in *hànzì*. Among them we find:

<i>Nǚshū</i> radical	Similar <i>hànzì</i> radical	Examples
堆		
怕		
唱		
捉		
埋		
鱼—魚		
故		
长		
青		
院		
时		
鬼		
把		

⁶¹ Wu, Op. cit., pp. 12.

⁶² Chen, J., Op. cit., pp. 59.

These radicals can be combined to form new components, which are placed in the same position within the character as the radicals themselves. Among them we can find:

Radical	Composition	Examples	Similar <i>hànzì</i> radical
	duplication of ㄩ	道	
	ㄩ + 丿	秋	
	ㄩ + 丿	梯	
	ㄩ + 丿	粗	
	duplication of ㄩ	往 and 倚	
	ㄩ + 丿	抢 and 独	亻
	+ a stroke above	福 and 祖	彳

Some radicals are used more frequently than others. Moreover, the progressive process of standardisation has eliminated many characters that shared the same main component but displayed numerous variations of radicals. After reviewing the word lists included in the works of Chiang and Gong, I found that the radicals and appear only once each, in the words (堵) and (经) respectively. However, these radicals, together with others mentioned in the previous paragraph, also appear as independent words. In these two cases, on its own represents characters such as 中, 张, 专, 江 and 公, whereas represents the characters 文 and 闻. Other radicals that function as independent characters include: (十, 事), (一), (飘, 批), (风, 睡), (界, 够), (要, 义) and (不, 未).

Although there is no direct relationship between the components of a *nǚzì* and the meaning of the *hànzì* it represents, these components can sometimes have a phonetic function. In other words, some *nǚzì* that share one component while differing in others may have a similar pronunciation. However, this is not a strictly consistent phenomenon. It may occur in the following situations:

- 1) Syllables whose initial and final sounds are identical but whose tones differ:

/tɕiu ³⁵ / 主 y 煮	
/tɕiu ³³ / 珠 y 具	

- 2) Syllables that share the same initial consonant but have different final vowels:

/ta ²¹ / 但	
/ta ³³ / 地	
/tao ⁴² / 逃	
/taŋ ⁴² / 唐	

- 3) Syllables whose initial consonants are different, while their medial and final elements are the same:

/saŋ ³³ / 双 y 桑	
/ɕioŋ ³³ / 声 y 兄	
/tsioŋ ⁴² / 情 y 亭	
/ts'ioŋ ³³ / 青 y 厅	
/t'anŋ ³³ / 汤 y 通	

Although some characters may also contain similar components, they do not necessarily represent pronunciations whose letters are identical or similar. For example:

/na ⁴² / 难	
/lioŋ ³⁵ / 顶	

 /eiou⁵⁵/ 法

 /kue²¹/ 驾

 /te'ueŋ³³/ 穿

 /tsi³³/ 焦

 /ka³³/ 间

 /ŋiu³³/ 玉

3.3. Differences between *nǚshū* and *nánshū*

The most accurate Chinese term for *nǚshū* 女书 is actually composed of three characters: “woman” 女, “book” 书, and “script” 文. However, the final character is often omitted, and in this context 书 is translated as “script” or “writing.” This term, referring to a writing system created by and for women, can be contrasted with the concept proposed by the researcher Fei-Wen Liu: *nánshū* 男书. This word is composed of “man” 男 and “book” 书, which, as in the previous case, can be translated here as “script.” It could be considered a synonym for *hànzì*, since it refers to the writing system used by men. In the past, *hànzì* were often associated with the male gender because the vast majority of women did not have access to education or to the learning of Chinese characters until well into the twentieth century. It was only then that some girls from wealthy families began to receive a very basic education at home, and a few were even able to attend schools established by foreign missionaries in cities that were more open to external influence⁶³. For this reason, *hànzì* were regarded as a writing system mainly associated with the literate male population and with men from middle- and upper-class backgrounds who aspired to positions in local or state government, since many peasants lacked the means to obtain a proper education.

Because these two writing systems were, in most cases, used by a specific gender, their uses in public and private life also differed. Although other writing systems existed in the country besides these two, such as the *dōngbā* script 东巴文 and the *gēbā* syllabary 哥巴文 belonging to the Naxi ethnic group 纳西族⁶⁴, Chinese characters were the

⁶³ French, M. and Atwood, M. (2008), p. 95.

⁶⁴ Officially recognised ethnic minority mainly inhabiting the provinces of Sichuan and Yunnan. Zhao, Op. cit., pp. 62.

principal medium used nationwide as a means of communication and representation of the official language.

Shangjiangxu and the surrounding municipalities were no exception, as *hànzì* were used both in the public sphere and in the educational domain. All governmental records, political propaganda, and teaching materials were written using Chinese characters. Other documents produced with this system included historical records, data related to land ownership, and genealogies in which the dates of birth, marriage, and death of all male members of the family were recorded. Women, however, rarely appeared in these records. Peasants also possessed a type of calendar containing information about the annual cycles of agriculture and other aspects related to geomancy. Finally, it is worth noting the local use of Chinese characters in invitations sent to relatives when an event was celebrated, posters placed in the streets announcing weddings, books used during marriage ceremonies where the birth dates of both individuals were written, and plaques dedicated to ancestors at funerals⁶⁵.

By contrast, *nǚshū* characters had very specific uses that were limited by the role of women within society. They were mainly used to write letters and decorate fans that were sent to relatives and sworn sisters, as well as biographies, autobiographies, books given to the bride on the third day after her wedding, and prayers to goddesses in which women asked, for example, to be granted a son in their next pregnancy.

These two writing systems also had very different moral connotations. The education and learning of Chinese characters was carried out through the reading of classical works from the Chinese tradition and therefore could be considered a way of strengthening the Confucian values that held great importance in traditional society and, to a lesser extent, still influence contemporary society. In this sense, they symbolised the somewhat “oppressive” role of men within a patriarchal social structure. By contrast, *nǚshū* provided women with a channel through which they could express their repressed feelings and reveal their reactions to this oppression⁶⁶. It also made possible the transformation of private emotional expression and crying—traditionally associated with

⁶⁵ Chiang, *Op. cit.*, pp. 71-72.

⁶⁶ Lee, L. L. (2002), pp. 106.

the female gender—into a practice that could be performed openly and publicly while remaining morally accepted by society⁶⁷.

Turning now to the aesthetic aspects of these writing systems, it should be noted that although certain similarities and correspondences exist between the forms of *nǚzì* and *hànzì*, the differences between them are more numerous. The strokes of *nǚshū* are longer, more curved, stylised, and elegant, qualities that may be associated with femininity and with the *yīn* 阴 aspect of the universe. By contrast, the strokes used to write Chinese characters are straighter and more rigid, since each character follows standardised forms, directions, and stroke orders. As mentioned earlier, *nǚzì* are composed of nine basic types of strokes that can produce a wide variety of shapes and basic components. *Hànzì*, on the other hand, are formed through eight basic strokes known as the “Eight Principles of the Character Yong” (*yǒngzìbāfǎ* 永字八法), which later developed into twenty-eight stroke styles⁶⁸. These eight strokes are: the horizontal line (横), the vertical line (竖), the rising stroke (提), the right-falling stroke (捺), the left-falling stroke (撇), the dot (点), the hook (钩), and the turning stroke (折). Once the strokes of both writing systems have been presented, the following differences can be identified⁶⁹:

- 1) *Nǚzì* include an arc-shaped stroke (弧) that cannot be directly compared to the left-falling stroke (撇). Unlike the latter, the arc can face either right or left, appear in different positions within the character, and vary in size.
- 2) Some *hànzì* strokes, such as the left-falling stroke (撇), are thinner at the beginning and thicker at the end. Other strokes may end with hooks, producing a rich variety of shapes. By contrast, *nǚshū* strokes, such as the left-slanting stroke (左斜), maintain a consistent thickness from beginning to end and do not include hook forms.
- 3) With the exception of the dot (圆点), the strokes of *nǚshū* are more irregular than those of Chinese characters; that is, they do not follow such strict patterns in terms of thickness. This may be explained by the fact that brushes and ink were not originally used for writing *nǚshū*, but rather sharper materials such

⁶⁷ Ibid., pp. 110.

⁶⁸ Wu, Op. cit., pp. 13.

⁶⁹ Ibid., pp. 13-14.

as bamboo sticks. *Hànzì*, by contrast, are typically written with brushes or other tools that allow the writer to control the flow of ink.

- 4) Both writing systems contain horizontal and vertical lines, but there is a calligraphic difference between them. In Chinese characters, pressure is applied with the brush when drawing these lines, making them thicker at the beginning. In *nǚshū*, however, the stroke remains uniform.
- 5) Both systems also include a stroke similar to the dot; however, in *nǚzì* it is round, whereas in *hànzì* it is elongated.

3.4. Writing media and their symbolism

The *nǚshū* script is mainly found on four types of material supports, each used in different contexts and serving a specific function. The object that usually attracts the attention of researchers and Western audiences interested in this topic is the fan. In Western contexts, this object has traditionally been used simply as a tool to relieve heat during warm seasons, but it has never served as a means of communication. In the Jiangyong region, however, fans were used to transmit messages between women who knew *nǚshū* and also as a tool for making prayers to the goddess Po⁷⁰. According to Chiang (1991: 142), the fans he was able to examine during his research were folding fans divided into eleven sections. In each section two lines of characters could be written, and they could also include floral and bird designs. Girls often used fans to send proposals for sworn sisterhoods to other girls from nearby villages, so they were among the many gifts exchanged when such a request was accepted.

Another medium on which *nǚzì* could be written or embroidered were handkerchiefs and fabrics used to make clothing. According to the surviving pieces, the handkerchiefs on which characters were written with ink were usually square and decorated with elements inspired by nature (figure 3). On the other hand, the fabrics on which designs and characters were embroidered tended to display colourful patterns (figure 4), which corresponds with the aesthetic characteristics of items produced within

⁷⁰ Gu Po 姑婆神, one of the three deities associated with marriage in Chinese culture. According to legend, Gu Po is not a single figure but rather two sister goddesses. Zhou, S. (1983), as cited in Chiang, Op. cit., pp. 142.

Yao culture and also allowed women to express different emotions and ideas through colour.

Figures 3 and 4: *Characters written (left) and embroidered (right) on handkerchiefs.*

Although fans could also be used to write letters, the most common format was red paper. This type of rice paper is very thin and is dyed red on one side, while the other side retains the original white colour with a slight reddish tint due to the translucent nature of the sheet. In China it is often used during special occasions such as national or local festivals to write auspicious messages and congratulations.

Chiang (1991: 137-141) explains that letters written in *nǚshū* were rectangular and could contain a horizontal line drawn between 2.5 and 7 centimetres from the upper edge, depending on the size of the sheet. The characters were first written on the red side, from top to bottom and from right to left, beginning at the upper right corner of the paper or from the area below the horizontal line if the writer had drawn one. In the latter case, upon reaching the lower left corner the writer continued writing just above the line near the left margin, turning the paper 90 degrees clockwise and writing a column downward along the line. When the lower edge was reached, the sheet was rotated 180 degrees in the same direction and writing continued downward; the paper was then rotated again in the same way, alternating the direction of the characters across several rows along the horizontal line, usually six or seven (figure 5). If the writer filled the entire red side and had not yet finished writing, she turned the sheet from left to right and continued writing from top to bottom and from right to left on the white side. The number of characters per row depended on the size of the sheet.

Once the letter was finished, it was first folded horizontally in one of two ways. It could be folded repeatedly to the right in intervals of about five centimetres until reaching the left edge of the letter, or it could be folded alternately forward and backward until the

end. It was then folded vertically twice downward, forming a small square or rectangle. The letter was usually delivered through another woman, for example during visits to relatives. Although men generally did not interfere in these “women’s matters” and could not fully understand the letter even if they tried to read it, it was nevertheless preferable that they did not take part in the process.

Figure 5: Reconstruction of a letter written on red paper⁷¹.

In addition to these formats, *nǚshū* was also written on paper in small rectangular booklets called *sānzhāoshū* 三朝书 or *hèsānzhāoshū* 贺三朝书, which can be translated as “third-day book,” since they were given to the bride on the third day of her wedding. These booklets contained between 9 and 15 folded sheets⁷² of cotton paper (*miánzhǐ* 棉纸) or rice paper (*xuānzhǐ* 宣纸)⁷³, depending on the writing tool used. Rice paper could be white or have a brownish tone. Initially, a sharpened bamboo stick was used, coated with a mixture of ashes and water to create a kind of ink⁷⁴, which produced the greyish-black colour of the characters and forms. This tool allowed writing on surfaces that could not be easily pierced, such as cotton paper, known for its durability and resistance over

⁷¹ The content of this self-composed letter is based on another letter written on a fan. See: <http://www.chinanvshu.cn/index.php?m=content&c=index&a=show&catid=29&id=183>

⁷² Chiang, Op. cit., pp. 134. Chen, H., Op. cit., pp. 33.

⁷³ Lee, A. G., Op. cit., pp. 109.

⁷⁴ Cheng, Y. (2016), pp. 23.

time. Rice paper, on the other hand, could only be written on with brush and ink because it is very thin and fragile, with much lower durability. Brushes could be made with hair from different animals, giving them particular characteristics and longevity.

The exterior of the *sānzhāoshū* was covered with a wrapper made of wood-based paper or fabric, typically black or blue, while the interior was lined with red paper. The right side of the cover, where the sheets were bound, was stitched vertically with thread and could include decorative designs such as flowers and geometric shape (figure 6)⁷⁵. The interior contained messages mainly written by members of the bride’s family on the first three or last folded sheets, while the remaining pages were left blank for the bride to write her own stories. The book opened from left to right and could contain writing from multiple people. Each contributor had to rotate the booklet and write on the next available page or the last one. On each sheet, a horizontal line was usually drawn about 3.5 centimetres from the top and bottom margins, confining the writing to the space between the lines. Characters were written from top to bottom and from right to left, forming about 7 to 8 columns of 9 to 12 characters per page⁷⁶.

Figures 6 y 7: exterior (left) and interior (right) of a “third-day book”.

The pages could include designs inspired by nature, and the corners could be decorated with red paper (figure 7). Often, the drawings were framed by an eight-sided shape called the octagonal flower (*bājiǎohuā* 八角花) (figure 8). This motif, commonly found in both embroidery and paper drawings, corresponds to the “eight trigrams” (*bāguà*

⁷⁵ Chen, H., Op. cit., pp. 33.

⁷⁶ Chiang, Op. cit., pp. 134-136.

八卦) of Taoism, a symbol composed of the eight trigrams surrounding the yin-yang (yīnyáng 阴阳)⁷⁷.

Figure 8: Drawing of a bird and flowers inside an octagonal flower.

Regarding the materials used in *nǚshū* works, Ann-Gee Lee (2008) argues that fabric, paper, ink, and bamboo have specific cultural connotations worth studying.

The cover of the third-day books was made of fabric, either cotton or silk. Cotton is a textile traditionally associated with women in China, as they were responsible for weaving it. Besides being used for clothing, cotton was also used in papermaking, offering greater durability than other materials. This links cotton to sworn relationships, since once a bond was established between girls, it often lasted a lifetime. Moreover, the character *mián* 棉 appears in the expression *chánchánmiánmián* 缠缠绵绵, symbolising the union of two people in love, which connects to the practice of giving these books to brides. In China, it is common to associate ideas through homophones, as in this case.

Silkworm rearing, cocoon processing, and spinning silk fibres were also tasks traditionally carried out by women. Silk was highly valued and strong, giving it rich symbolism. The term silk is used metaphorically to refer positively to women's hair, emotional sensitivity, and delicate tastes.⁷⁸ Thus, silk embodies qualities historically associated with women.

⁷⁷ Chen, H., Op. cit., pp. 49-50.

⁷⁸ Lee, A. G., Op. cit., pp. 116-117.

In Chinese tradition, paper was mainly linked to scholars and education, as illiterate people from lower social classes had no need to use it. In Hunan, however, women also used paper and could write characters created specifically for them, symbolising empowerment in a patriarchal society. Furthermore, the character for paper, *zhǐ* 纸, contains the silk radical, connecting it to the ideas above. Rice paper could be dyed red on one side and was used for both letters and decorating the interior of third-day books. Red symbolises happiness, good fortune, and energy in Chinese tradition. In the Five Elements theory (*wǔxíng* 五行), red is associated with the heart 心, understood as both heart and mind, the most important part of the human body. For this reason, red is used in major life celebrations such as weddings and the Spring Festival (*chūnjié* 春节).

Like paper, ink could also be associated with the educated class. However, the ink used by women writing *nǚshū* was homemade from ashes, unlike the scholars' ink. According to Lee, the character for ink *mò* 墨 is a homophone of *mò* 莫, meaning “not,” which could symbolise eternal bonds and friendship among sworn sisters. Since women exchanged messages written in ink, it carried strong symbolism: the words written with this pigment would always accompany their sisters, so they would not feel alone even if separated by distance.

Bamboo, in contrast, symbolises intelligence and resilience. Its thin trunk may seem fragile but is actually very flexible. The character for bamboo *zhú* 竹 appears in the expression *shìrúpòzhú* 势如破竹, meaning to remain firm and keep moving forward. Bamboo withstands pressure without breaking, an idea that can be related to the strength of women in ancient China, who endured patriarchal oppression yet continued their lives. Sworn sisters were pillars supporting each other during difficult times, offering comfort and help to remain steadfast like bamboo. Another symbolic meaning of bamboo is filial piety, illustrated in the popular tale «*Meng Zong crying over bamboo shoots*» 《孟宗哭竹》, from «*Twenty-four Examples of Filial Piety*» 《二十四孝》 by Guo Jujing 郭居敬 during the Yuan Dynasty 元朝 (1260–1368). In the story, Meng Zong's mother was seriously ill and wished to eat bamboo shoots, but they were not yet harvestable. The young man went to the bamboo grove, held the shoots while crying, and his tears made the bamboo grow. The soup he made with them cured his mother, exemplifying filial piety.

In this way, each primary element used in creating *nǚshū* works has a specific cultural connotation. While women had defined roles and virtues in society—often determined by men—they found in writing a means of expression and, in a way, resistance to the patriarchal system. These materials symbolise resilience, spiritual strength, and the creation of a collective consciousness among women, giving them a silent tool to confront traditional Confucian values.

3.5. Composition of texts and poetic devices

Written compositions in *nǚshū*, such as letters, autobiographies, and songs, are primarily structured through three main aspects: metrical pattern, rhyme, and rhythm. Many texts were written in the form of narrative poems, typically composed of seven-character lines, a convention inherited from earlier generations. However, this was not strictly followed, as the flexible nature of the script allowed writers to choose the length of their verses. As a result, we also find poems in which the number of characters per line varies.

One difference between *nǚshū* poetry and classical Chinese poetry lies in the number of lines composing the text. Traditional Chinese poems could follow patterns of five characters (*wǔlǜ* 五律 and *wǔjué* 五绝), or seven characters, as in *nǚshū* (*qīlǜ* 七律 and *qījué* 七绝). In contrast, *nǚshū* poems did not adhere strictly to these patterns; their texts could range from just a few lines to hundreds, as seen in folk tales and songs. The length of the text was determined by the emotion being expressed: longer poems conveyed more detailed and elaborate ideas, while shorter ones emphasised the writer's feelings and intensity⁷⁹.

This type of seven-character narrative composition can be related to two concepts from the Chinese literary tradition: *biànwén* 变文 and *táncí* 弹词. *Biànwén* is a popular narrative literary form that emerged during the Tang dynasty 唐朝 (618-907) to recount episodes from the life of the Buddha, though it was later used for stories from Chinese history and tradition. Like *táncí*, it combines prose and verse—two forms also found in *nǚshū* literature due to its sung and spoken modes of expression. *Táncí*, which developed during the Ming dynasty 明朝 (1368-1644), was used by women in regions around the

⁷⁹ He, Op. cit., pp. 28.

Yangtze River and was later adopted by women in Jiangyong to compose their own texts. Like *nǚshū*, its verses typically consisted of seven characters, although they could sometimes extend up to ten⁸⁰.

It is worth noting that early texts were written continuously, without punctuation marks separating sentences. These were only introduced in more recent periods by later generations⁸¹.

Rhyme in *nǚshū* texts usually occurred in the final character of each line, with even-numbered lines rhyming while odd-numbered ones remained unrhymed. However, this was not strictly enforced, and some lines in the middle of a poem might not rhyme. For words to rhyme, they needed to share syllables with identical medial and final sounds, while the initial consonant could differ⁸². This differs from classical Chinese poetry, where rhyming syllables also had to belong to the same tonal group. It is important to note that the tones of some words in classical Chinese differed from those in modern Mandarin. In poetic composition, tones were divided into two groups: first and second tones formed one group, while third and fourth tones formed another. Thus, a character pronounced in the first tone could rhyme with one in the second tone, but not with those in the third or fourth tones.

An example of rhyme in a *nǚshū* text can be seen in the following excerpt:

Line 1	几人有福登金殿 tei ³⁵ ŋie ³³ you ²¹ fu ⁵⁵ lai ³³ teie ³³ teŋ ³³	Line 2	几人无福丧边疆 tei ³⁵ ŋie ³³ vu ⁴² fu ⁵⁵ saŋ ²¹ peŋ ³³ teiaŋ ³³
Line 3	几人夜宿红罗帐 tei ³⁵ ŋie ³³ yue ³³ siou ⁵⁵ hai ⁴² leu ⁴² teiaŋ ²¹	Line 4	几人无被到天光 tei ³⁵ ŋie ³³ vu ⁴² pa ²¹ lao ²¹ t'ej ³³ kaŋ ³³
Line 5	几人有饭无人饮 tei ³⁵ ŋie ³³ you ²¹ paŋ ³³ vu ⁴² ŋie ³³ ye ³⁵	Line 6	几人无米粥清汤 tei ³⁵ ŋie ³³ vu ⁴² mi ²¹ teiou ⁵⁵ ts'ioŋ ³³ t'aŋ ³³
Line 7	几人无妻孤自独 tei ³⁵ ŋie ³³ vu ⁴² ts'i ³³ ku ³³ tse ³³ tu ³³	Line 8	几人三女共夫郎 tei ³⁵ ŋie ³³ soŋ ³³ ŋiu ²¹ teiaŋ ³³ fu ³³ laŋ ⁴²
Line 9	世上几人登百岁 ei ²¹ ciaŋ ²¹ tei ³⁵ ŋie ³³ lai ³³ pe ⁵⁵ eu ²¹	Line 10	几人在娘怀内亡 tei ³⁵ ŋie ³³ tso ²¹ ŋiaŋ ⁴² fo ⁴² na ³³ vaŋ ⁴²
Line 11	西天取经唐三藏 si ³³ t'ej ³³ te'u ³⁵ teieŋ ³³ taŋ ⁴² soŋ ³³ tsaŋ ⁴²	Line 12	暮里陈府去寻娘... mu ³³ la ²¹ teie ⁴² fu ³⁵ hu ²¹ teue ⁴² ŋiaŋ ⁴²
Line 13	千里送衣孟姜女 ts'ej ³³ la ²¹ sai ²¹ o ³³ ma ³³ teiaŋ ³³ ŋiu ²¹	Line 14	贞心女子去寻郎 teie ³³ sai ³³ ŋiu ²¹ tse ³⁵ hu ²¹ teue ⁴² laŋ ⁴²
Line 15	夫妻不说长短话	Line 16	皆是前生注定来...

⁸⁰ Wang, Op. cit., pp. 178.

⁸¹ Ma, Op. cit., pp. 22.

⁸² He, Op. cit., pp. 29.

	fu ³³ ts ³³ i ³³ me ²¹ eu ⁵⁵ teian ³⁵ lan ³⁵ fe ³³		ko ³³ se ²¹ tseŋ ⁴² sa ³³ teu ²¹ tsion ³³ la ²¹
Line 17	秋湖祖大家豪富	Line 18	鸟飞不过好田庄
	ts ³³ iou ³³ hu ⁴² tsu ³⁵ to ³³ kue ³³ hao ⁴² fu ²¹		li ³⁵ fa ³³ me ²¹ ku ²¹ hao ²¹ teŋ ⁴² tsaŋ ³³
Line 19	媒人说话罗家女	Line 20	天上一对好成双...
	meŋ ⁴² ŋie ³³ eu ⁵⁵ fe ³³ leu ⁴² kue ³³ ŋiu ²¹		t ³³ eiŋ ³³ eiŋ ²¹ yi ⁵⁵ lie ²¹ hao ²¹ eiŋ ⁴² saŋ ³³
Line 21	娶得罗氏方六日	Line 22	秋湖腹中便思量
	te ³³ u ³⁵ leu ⁵⁵ leu ⁴² se ²¹ fan ³³ liou ³³ ai ³³		ts ³³ iou ³³ hu ⁴² pu ⁵⁵ teian ³³ peŋ ³³ se ³³ lian ³³
Line 23	便去房前日父母	Line 24	我要求官去科场
	peŋ ³³ hu ²¹ paŋ ⁴² tseŋ ⁴² ai ³³ fu ²¹ mu ²¹		ŋu ²¹ ŋie ³³ teiou ⁴² kaŋ ³³ hu ²¹ k ³³ u ³³ teian ⁴²
Line 25	便请诸请并六眷	Line 26	谢尔服侍二尊堂...
	peŋ ³³ ts ³³ ioŋ ³⁵ teu ³³ ts ³³ ioŋ ³⁵ pion ²¹ liou ³³ teuŋ ²¹		tsie ³³ ei ⁵⁵ fu ³³ se ³³ na ³³ teue ³³ taŋ ⁴²

In this fragment, taken from Xie Zhimin's work (1991: 1294-1361)⁸³, we observe that most even-numbered lines rhyme with each other, as their final character has a pronunciation consisting of a consonant + the vowel /a/ + the final consonant /ŋ/ (/ng/ in *pǔtōnghuà*). There are also lines that do not have this exact ending but a very similar one, as seen in the underlined characters (lines 2, 12, 22, and 24), whose pronunciation follows the pattern consonant + vowels /ia/ + /ŋ/. Finally, line 16 is the only one that does not follow either of these patterns and therefore remains unrhymed. The tones of these syllables alternate between /33/ and /42/.

Nǚshū texts were performed orally in the form of free singing without musical accompaniment, through which a particular tone and rhythm were expressed according to the singer and the emotion conveyed in the text⁸⁴. He Xiarong (2011: 29), citing Zhang Ying (2006: 16-24), explains that this singing belonged to the genre of vocal music and was performed *a cappella* by a single person. However, other accounts indicate that it could also be performed in groups. Although each woman could freely choose her vocal tone, it was generally limited to three categories: original or prototype tones (*yuánxíng yīndiào* 原型音调), modified tones (*biànxíng yīndiào* 变型音调), and borrowed tones (*jièyòng yīndiào* 借用音调). The tempo of the singing was determined by the content of the song and was also a personal choice. This flexibility in tone and rhythm made it easier to master the recitation of texts.

Since these compositions took the form of poetry, writers employed various literary devices to aid memorisation, recitation, and aesthetic expression. One of these is parallelism, a figure of speech involving the repetition of structures or words across

⁸³ As cited in He, Op. cit., pp. 28-29.

⁸⁴ Ibid., pp. 29.

different lines. Repetition plays a key role in learning and transmitting texts across generations or among groups of women. A text with repeated words or structures is easier to memorise both for the performer and the listeners, who can retain it after hearing it several times. In the previously analysed fragment, titled «Miss Luo» 《罗氏女》, this device appears repeatedly in lines one through ten. For example:

几人有福登金殿 / 几人无福丧边疆
 几人夜宿红罗帐 / 几人无被到天光
 几人有饭无人饮 / 几人无米粥清汤

Here we observe the repetition of the structure 几人 in the odd lines and 几人无 in the even lines. Their translation would be “some people (do)” and “some people do not,” respectively, showing a contrast of opposites, which is known as antithesis. Another example combining these devices appears in the same text:

男人十五无官职 / 枉出男儿读文章
 At fifteen, a man holds no official post;
 in vain he has studied the classics.
 女人十五无针钱 / 枉出闺女在娘房⁸⁵
 At fifteen, a woman earns nothing from her needle;
 in vain she remains in her maiden chamber.

In this case, the repeated structure is noun + 十五无 (“at fifteen, does not...”) in the odd lines, and 枉出 (“in vain”) + noun + action in the even lines. We can also observe contrasts between man and woman (男人 and 女人) in the odd lines and between boy and girl (男儿 and 闺女) in the even lines.

Another poetic device involving repetition is anadiplosis, which consists of repeating a word or expression at the end of one line and at the beginning of the next, such as:

戴个斗笠哭起来，哭到广西去读书
 读书三年得入学，入学三年得作官
 作官三年官任满，作官四年回本乡⁸⁶

⁸⁵ Xie, Z. (1991), pp.1313, as cited in He, Op. cit., pp. 26.

⁸⁶ Zhao, Op. cit., pp. 77.

In this fragment, we can observe the repetition of 哭 (to cry), 读书 (to study), 入学 (to begin schooling), and 作官 (to become an official), which serve to connect the six lines to one another.

Another literary device used is metaphor, although it is often more difficult to analyse, as it requires a deep understanding of Mandarin and Chinese poetry. A simple example would be 一马二鞍人难坐 / 一女二夫丑名声⁸⁷, which can be translated as: “A horse with two saddles is difficult to ride; a woman with two husbands has a bad reputation”, This compares the situation of the horse with that of the woman, presenting both as inappropriate situations that should be avoided. Another example is 自从盘古开天地 / 一朝天子一朝臣⁸⁸, which can be translated as: “Since Pangu⁸⁹ separated heaven and earth, each emperor brings his own ministers.” Here, we can observe a comparison and distinction between a superior entity (heaven and the emperor) and an inferior one (earth and the ministers).

In these texts written by women, descriptions of landscapes and weather are uncommon unless they are used metaphorically. For example, the expression 有天没日头 (“There is a sky but no sun”) can be used to express a miserable moment or life. Likewise, references to the sky and clouds may symbolise sadness and sorrow⁹⁰. Flowers and animals are also frequently used to construct metaphors. Flowers may symbolise femininity, as well as fate and friendship among women⁹¹. Among the animals mentioned, mandarin ducks are particularly significant, as they represent the eternity of a bond. It is said that once they find a partner, they remain together for life; thus, they can symbolise not only romantic relationships but also the bond between sworn sisters.

As in embroidery, homophones were also essential in the composition of texts, as they allowed the writer to choose from a wider range of terms and to imbue her words with symbolic meaning. The example of the character for “good fortune” associated with bats and butterflies is also applicable here. By using words or images representing these creatures, the writer could be alluding to good luck.

⁸⁷ Xie (1991:1531), as cited in He, *Op. cit.*, pp. 27.

⁸⁸ Xie (1991:1491), as cited in *Ibid.*, pp. 27.

⁸⁹ Pan Gu 盘古, the creator deity of the universe in Chinese mythology.

⁹⁰ Zhao., *Op. cit.*, pp. 73.

⁹¹ *Ibid.*, pp. 74.

Numbers are another element with strong symbolic value in Chinese culture and in these poems. According to He (2011: 33–34), an analysis of *nǚshū* texts shows that odd numbers appear more frequently than even numbers. Within Taoist theory, numbers are understood as a union of opposites: odd numbers correspond to *yang* energy, while even numbers correspond to *yin*. Thus, odd numbers are associated with the masculine, and even numbers with the feminine. Since odd numbers appear frequently in these texts, this may reflect traditional Chinese society, characterised by a patriarchal system in which men held a higher status than women. However, the author also proposes that the simultaneous presence of both even and odd numbers may symbolise women's desire for a more egalitarian society, in which everyone has equal opportunities and existing hierarchies are eliminated.

3.6. Themes

The *nǚshū* script was not only used to narrate the lives and experiences of women in Jiangyong but also reflected cultural and social aspects. Letters, fans, third-day books, and other records could contain complaints about the prevailing system in China as well as notes on past and present events. These texts generally reflect the five recurring themes of Chinese literature—good fortune (*fú* 福), prosperity (*lù* 禄), longevity (*shòu* 寿), happiness (*xǐ* 喜), and wealth (*cái* 财)—adapted to the female sphere through the use of natural imagery and cultural elements. Thus, they make use of words and expressions that evoke flowers, birds, insects, and fish, as well as other cultural allegories such as the Eight Immortals (*bāxiān* 八仙), the Seven Fairies (*qīxiānnǚ* 七仙女), and the dragon and the phoenix (*lóngfēng* 龙凤)⁹².

The stories and narratives recorded through *nǚshū* were usually appealing to women because they contained useful information and were relatively easy to memorise, even when some were quite long. Among the recorded songs we find «*The Song of Embroidery*» 《绣花歌》 which describes embroidery patterns, and «*The Song of the Twenty-Four Solar Terms*» 《二十四节气歌》 which refers to the periods into which the agricultural year is divided. The stories often featured famous women from antiquity,

⁹² Chen, H., Op. cit., pp. 47.

such as the legend of Liang Shanbo and Zhu Yingtai, known as «*The butterfly lovers*» 《梁山伯与祝英台》 or «*Lady Meng Jiang*» 《孟姜女》⁹³.

In some cases, classical texts that women were expected to know—especially those dealing with proper behaviour or Confucian values—were also transcribed into women’s script. For example, the «*Four-Character Classic for Women*» 《四字女经》 was adapted in this way⁹⁴.

Accounts recording real historical events were produced in more recent periods compared to those focusing on women’s lives. We know that these texts date from the 19th and 20th centuries because they include events such as the Taiping Rebellion (1850-1864) in «*Guo Yongming’s Taiping Heavenly Kingdom*» 《太平天国郭永明》, the Sino-Japanese Wars (1894-1895 and 1937-1945) in «*Chronicles of the Sino-Japanese War*» 《中日战争记事歌》, and the feminist revolution (from the 20th century onward) in «*Song of Liberation*» 《解放歌》⁹⁵. In addition to events of national significance, local occurrences in the Jiangyong area—such as weddings, funerals, and other community events—were also recorded. This demonstrates that, although women’s participation in public life was restricted and they rarely left their homes, they nevertheless possessed considerable knowledge of what was happening around them⁹⁶.

A recurring theme in letters written by women is the Buddhist concept of karma, especially in relation to being born female. There are frequent references to the idea that being born a woman in one’s present life is the result of accumulated misdeeds in a previous life and is therefore seen as a form of divine punishment. In this way, many women explained the misfortunes they experienced. Complaints about the patriarchal system and the perceived injustice of male superiority are also common. This is reflected in expressions such as: “*Do not blame your parents for marrying you off so young; blame only the Jade Emperor⁹⁷ for establishing the wrong rules [of conduct]*”⁹⁸.

In letters exchanged between sworn sisters, a wide range of emotions can be found. Women wrote not only to congratulate one another or to offer help and comfort, but also

⁹³ Chiang, Op. cit., pp. 156-159.

⁹⁴ Ibid., pp. 168.

⁹⁵ Zhao, Op. cit., pp. 69-70.

⁹⁶ Chiang, Op. cit., pp. 165.

⁹⁷ Yu Di 玉帝, the deity who rules the heavens according to Taoist philosophy.

⁹⁸ Zhao, L. (1991) (Zhou, S., Trad.), pp. 178, as cited in Silber (1994), Op. cit., pp. 63.

during conflicts. At times, they expressed dissatisfaction and even accused their husbands of inappropriate behaviour. Therefore, *nǐshū* functioned as a tool through which women could openly and directly express their feelings, circumventing the social norms that imposed passive and indirect forms of expression upon them.

According to Luo (2016: 14), of the approximately 600 collected pieces of writing, 429 can be identified and grouped into three main themes. The first is the longing for a pure friendship with another woman that transcends blood ties. The emphasis on purity is important because some researchers have suggested that such intimate relationships between women could develop into homosexual feelings. While this occurred in other types of female associations in China, I agree with scholars such as Gong in arguing that this was not the case here. Therefore, such expressions should be understood as innocent messages of friendship, without further implications. Relationships between sworn sisters were often stronger than kinship ties, as they involved communication between equals who understood each other's suffering as their own. As a result, girls who wished to establish such bonds highly valued both their sisters and their friendship, making this a recurring theme in these writings.

The second theme is a happy marriage associated with true love. In most cases, young couples did not know each other before marriage, making it impossible to understand each other's personalities beforehand. It was common for marriages not to meet expectations, yet couples were expected to learn to love each other or at least maintain a harmonious life together. Many women therefore longed to be matched with a man who would love and treat them well, although reality was often very different. As a result, many suffered in silence and felt the need to communicate with their sworn sisters.

The third most common theme is the desire to gain acceptance, affection, and respect from the husband's family. After marriage, women became part of their husband's family, often subject to his authority as well as that of his parents or other relatives. Some texts express the sorrow of women who suffered mistreatment after moving into their husband's household, including instances of abuse. Since family is a central aspect of Chinese life, women longed to belong to a supportive and welcoming environment where they would be valued as full members rather than treated as outsiders or threats.

Conclusions

After completing this research, several final considerations can be drawn in relation to the objectives initially established. Regarding the first objective, which aimed to define the geographical scope and examine the cultural aspects surrounding *nǚshū*, the following conclusions can be reached: this script was historically used in a very specific area of China, within a community shaped by a blend of Han and Yao ethnic groups. Its origin remains unknown, although numerous theories have been proposed. While ritual relationships between women were not exclusive to this community, they played a crucial role in the development and expansion of *nǚshū*. As its practice and transmission were facilitated, it became a fundamental means of communication and a tool for fostering female collective identity. The marriage system also contributed to its spread across neighbouring areas. The script was socially accepted, as it was present in everyday life and in wedding rituals. Unfortunately, the social changes and political conflicts that took place during the 19th and 20th centuries led to its temporary disappearance and subsequent rediscovery.

With regard to the second objective, which focused on the phonetic and graphic analysis of this women's script, the following conclusions can be drawn: from a phonetic perspective, *nǚshū* represents the Xiangnan *tǔhuà* dialect, whose phonetic system is difficult to analyse with complete accuracy due to tonal variation between localities and the standardisation carried out in recent decades. The script represents a limited number of syllables, and dialectal influence can be observed in certain expressions (fixed forms).

From a graphic perspective, the characters appear to derive from three main sources and show a clear influence from Chinese characters (*hànzì*). Structurally, they can be classified as simple or compound forms. Although they contain components that function similarly to radicals, these do not convey meaning. In some cases, the components may serve a phonetic function. In Shangjiangxu, both Chinese characters and *nǚzì* were used, although they were associated with different genders, practical uses, and moral values. The script appears on four types of material supports, each with its own uses and characteristics; the materials themselves may also carry symbolic meaning. Texts are primarily composed in poetic form, generally following flexible conventions, and show influences from traditional literary forms. They also incorporate common poetic

devices and culturally significant imagery. The recurring themes correspond to the everyday concerns of local women.

Regarding the first point, most of the consulted sources agree with the conclusions presented here; the main difference lies in the depth of analysis. However, it has been much more challenging to draw conclusions about the oral and written features. By comparing and evaluating the perspectives found in previous studies, I have attempted to justify my interpretations as clearly and simply as possible.

During this research, I encountered two main limitations. The first, methodological in nature, is the scarcity of original sources currently preserved. The fact that many documents were destroyed in the past—either due to political conflicts or by the women themselves—makes it difficult to uncover new information that could update existing knowledge. As a result, many aspects remain unknown, and current research is based on the limited testimonies available. The second limitation, of a more personal nature, concerns access to Chinese sources. Most Western researchers have approached this topic from a cultural perspective, whereas my interest lies in the features closely linked to the dialect represented through *nǚshū* and the form of its characters. I found that several studies by Chinese scholars address these aspects but accessing them from my geographical location proved difficult. Consequently, I had to rely on native speakers to help me obtain these materials. Fortunately, linguistic and cultural differences did not ultimately hinder the completion of this research.

Given the aforementioned scarcity of original materials, it is difficult for future research to present entirely new findings that have not already been discussed. Nevertheless, one should not lose hope: new documents may yet be discovered, shedding light on the incomplete information currently available. Alternatively, future studies may approach the topic from different practical or social perspectives, offering new insights and conclusions beyond those reached by current sinological research. *Nǚshū* was not only a valuable tool for women oppressed within traditional Chinese society but also holds great historical and cultural significance for sinologists. Thanks to its rediscovery, we now have insight into the lives and thoughts of ordinary people—especially women—whose voices have rarely been reflected in historical records and elite literature over the past centuries. Thus, *nǚshū* can be understood both as a means of expression and liberation for women of the past, and as a window through which scholars can observe

their joys and hardships, fostering a sense of empathy for the difficult conditions in which they lived alongside their cherished companions.

Bibliographical references

- Bai, S. (2019): *húnán jiāngyǒng shàngjiāngxū nǚshū fāyuándì tǔhuà yǔyīn yánjiū* 湖南江永上江圩女书发源地土话语音研究 (Phonetic study of the dialect in the place of origin of *nǚshū* in Jiangyong, Hunan). [Master's thesis, Hunan Normal University].
- Chen, H. (2013): *yǒngzhōu nǚshū wénhuà fúhào de xiàngzhēng yánjiū* 永州女书文化符号的象征研究 (A study on the symbolism of *nǚshū* cultural symbols in Yongzhou) [Master's thesis, Jiangnan University].
- Chen, J. (1986): *shìxī nǚshū xíng yīn yì de tèdiǎn* 试析女书形音义的特点 (A tentative analysis of the characteristics of form, sound, and meaning in *nǚshū*). In: Gong, Z., *fùnǚ wénzì hé yáozú qiānjiā dòng* 妇女文字和瑶族千家峒 (Women's script and Qianjiadong of the Yao ethnic group), pp. 42-60. Beijing: zhongguo zhanwang chubanshe.
- Cheng, Y. (2016): *nǚshū zìtǐ de túxíng huà yánjiū yǔ yìngyòng* 女书字体的图形化研究与应用 (Research and application of the graphic forms of *nǚshū* characters). [Master's thesis, North China University of Science and Engineering].
- Chiang, W. W. (1991): *"We two know the script; we have become good friends": Linguistic and social aspects of the Women's Script literacy in Southern Hunan, China*. [Doctoral dissertation, Yale University].
- Croll, E. (2011): *Feminism and socialism in China*. Oxford, Canada, and New York: Routledge (Taylor & Francis Group).
- French, M. y Atwood, M. (2008): *From Eve to Dawn: Revolutions and the Struggles for Justice in the 20th Century* (vol. 4). New York: The Feminist Press.
- Gong, Z. (1986): *fùnǚ wénzì hé yáozú qiānjiā dòng* 妇女文字和瑶族千家峒 (Women's script and Qianjiadong of the Yao ethnic group). Beijing: zhongguo zhanwang chubanshe.

- He, X. (2011): *duōchóng shìjiǎo xià de nǚshū jí nǚshū wénhuà yánjiū* 多重视角下的女书及女书文化研究 (A multi-perspective study of *nǚshū* and its culture). [Doctoral dissertation, Central China Normal University].
- Huang, Xuezheng (1993): *jiāngyǒng fāngyán yánjiū* 江永方言研究 (A study of the Jiangyong dialect). Beijing: shehui kexue wenxian chubanshe.
- Huang, Xuefei (1986): *shàngjiāngxūxiāng xiáolǐcūn de fùnǚ* 上江圩乡峭里村的妇女 (Women of Xiaoli village in Shangjiangxu). In: Gong, Z., *fùnǚ wénzì hé yáozú qiānjiā dòng* 妇女文字和瑶族千家峒 (Yao ethnic group women's and Qianjiadong writing), pp. 124-125. Beijing: zhongguo zhanwang chubanshe.
- Huang, H. (1986): *xiāojiāngxiāng báishuǐ, jiānghécūn de “nǚshū”* 消江乡白水、江河村的“女书” (*Nǚshū* in Baishui and Jianghe villages of Xiaojiang). In: Gong, Z., *fùnǚ wénzì hé yáozú qiānjiā dòng* 妇女文字和瑶族千家峒 (Yao ethnic group women's and Qianjiadong writing), pp. 139-141. Beijing: zhongguo zhanwang chubanshe.
- Idema, W. L. (2009): *Heroines of Jiangyong: Chinese narrative ballads in women's script*. Seattle: University of Washington Press.
- Lee, A. G. (2008): *Female Fabrications: An Examination of the Public and Private Aspects of Nüshu*. [Doctoral dissertation, Graduate College of Bowling Green State University].
- Lee, L. L. (2002): Creating a Female Language: Symbolic Transformation Embedded in Nushu. In: Lu, X. et al., *Chinese Communication Studies: Contexts and Comparisons*, pp. 101-118. United States: Greenwood Publishing Group.
- Litzinger, R. A. (1995): Making Histories Contending Conceptions of the Yao Past. In: Harrell, S., *Cultural Encounters on China's Ethnic Frontiers*, pp. 117-139. Seattle: University of Washington Press.
- Liu, F. W. (2004a): *From Being to Becoming: Nüshu and Sentiments in a Chinese Rural Community*. *American Ethnologist*, 31(3), 422-439.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/3805367>
- Liu, F. W. (2004b): *Literacy, Gender and Class: Nüshu and Sisterhood Communities in*

Southern Rural Hunan. *Nan Nü: Men, Women, and Gender in China*, 6(2), 241-82. DOI: [10.1163/1568526042530427](https://doi.org/10.1163/1568526042530427).

Liu, F. W. (2010): *Narrative, Genre, and Contextuality: The "Nüshu"-Transcribed Liang-Zhu Ballad in Rural South China*. *Asian Ethnology*, 69(2), 241-264. <https://asianethnology.org/articles/328>

Luo, X. (2016): *fēi wùzhì wénhuà yíchǎn zhōng húnán jiāngyǒng nǚshū chuántǒng túxíng de chuánchéng yǔ yùnyòng yánjiū* 非物质文化遗产中湖南江永女书传统图形的传承与运用研究 (Transmission and application of traditional *nǚshū* graphic forms as intangible cultural heritage). [Master's thesis, Hunan Normal University].

Ma, W. (2009): *jiāngyǒng nǚshū wénzì de xìngzhì yánjiū* 江永女书文字的性质研究 (A study on the nature of *nǚshū* writing). [Master's thesis, Hunan Normal University].

Sankar, A. (1978): *The Evolution of the Sisterhood in Traditional Chinese Society: From Village Girls' Houses to Chai T'angs in Hong Kong*. [Doctoral dissertation, University of Michigan].

See, L. (Ed. 2006): *Snow Flower and the Secret Fan*. Salamandra.

Silber, C. (1994): From Daughter to Daughter-in-law in the Women's Script of Southern Hunan. In: Gilmartin, C. K. et al., *Engendering China: Women, Culture, and the State*, pp. 47-68. Cambridge, Massachusetts, London, England: Harvard University Press.

Silber, C. (1995): *Nüshu (Chinese women's script) Literacy and Literature*. [Doctoral dissertation, University of Michigan].

The Nushu Coder's Group on GitHub (2018-2020): *zàixiàn nǚ shū zìdiǎn* 在线女书字典 (*Online nǚshū dictionary*). Retrieved April 8, 2021, from <https://nushuscript.org/>

Tsinghua University (2017): *nǚshū shì shénme* 女书是什么 (what is *nǚshū*?). Retrieved April 30, 2021, from <http://www.thurcaccia.org/bookpage/1/>

Wang, P. (2000): *Aching for Beauty: Footbinding in China*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.

Wei, Y. (1986): *shàngjiāngxūxiāng xiàwāncūn de "nǚshū"* 上江圩乡夏湾村的“女

- 书” (“*Nǚshū*” in Xiawan Village of Shangjiangxu). In: Gong, Z., *fùnǚ wénzì hé yáozú qiānjiā dòng* 妇女文字和瑶族千家峒 (Yao ethnic group women's and Qianjiadong writing), pp. 126-133. Beijing: zhongguo zhanwang chubanshe.
- Wu, Y. (2013): *jiāngyǒng nǚshū wénzì zàoxíng jí shèjì yìngyòng yánjiū* 江永女书文字造型及设计应用研究 (Research on the application of the form and design of Jiangyong's *nǚshū* script). [Master's thesis, Hunan University].
- Xiao, S. (1986): *dào xiàn tiánguǎngdòng cūn de “nǚshū”* 道县田广洞村的“女书” (“*Nǚshū*” in Tianguangdong Village, Dao County). In: Gong, Z., *fùnǚ wénzì hé yáozú qiānjiā dòng* 妇女文字和瑶族千家峒 (Yao ethnic group women's and Qianjiadong writing), pp. 142-144. Beijing: zhongguo zhanwang chubanshe.
- Zhang, X. (1986): *shàngjiāngxūxiāng pǔwěicūn de “nǚshū”* 上江圩乡莆尾村的“女书” (“*Nǚshū*” in Puwei Village of Shangjiangxu). In: Gong, Z., *fùnǚ wénzì hé yáozú qiānjiā dòng* 妇女文字和瑶族千家峒 (Yao ethnic group women's and Qianjiadong writing), pp. 134-135. Beijing: zhongguo zhanwang chubanshe.
- Zhao, L. (1986): *nǚshū——yī zhǒng tèshū de fùnǚ wénxué* 女书——一种特殊的妇女文学 (“*Nǚshū*”, a special form of writing for women). In: Gong, Z., *fùnǚ wénzì hé yáozú qiānjiā dòng* 妇女文字和瑶族千家峒 (Yao ethnic group women's and Qianjiadong writing), pp. 61-84. Beijing: zhongguo zhanwang chubanshe.
- Zhao, L. y Gong, Z. (1986): *“nǚzì” zàozì fǎ chūtàn “nǚzì” zàozì fǎ chūtàn* “女字”造字法初探 (On the formation of *nǚshū* characters). In: Gong, Z., *fùnǚ wénzì hé yáozú qiānjiā dòng* 妇女文字和瑶族千家峒 (Yao ethnic group women's and Qianjiadong writing), pp. 85-97. Beijing: zhongguo zhanwang chubanshe.

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Jinghua). Jiangyong Tourism Development Centre, 2020. Digital Museum of *nǚshū*.

<http://www.chinanvshu.cn/index.php?m=content&c=index&a=show&catid=29&id=180>

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<http://www.chinanvshu.cn/index.php?m=content&c=index&a=show&catid=29&id=185>

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<http://www.chinanvshu.cn/index.php?m=content&c=index&a=show&catid=29&id=202&page=6>